

Highlights

Minority Signal Dilution Under Extreme Class Imbalance: Implications for CTGAN–SMOTE Hybrid Oversampling in Industrial AI

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- SMOTE–CTGAN combination benefits industrial imbalanced data only above $IR \approx 130:1$.
- Minority-only GAN training (A4) outperforms balanced-data GAN (A3) at high IR.
- Minority Signal Dilution (MSD) effect in A3 identified: majority data dilutes fault-learning signal.
- SDR + IR dual condition is consistent with the observed optimal strategy on all 10 evaluated datasets.
- Validated on SECOM, Steel Faults, AI4I (TWF, PWF, OSF) industrial engineering benchmarks across all three SDR regimes.
- Theory-predicted no-ordering outcome observed on AI4I-PWF (SDR=11.88) and AI4I-OSF (SDR=12.25), both above their dataset-specific $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$.
- Practitioner protocol: IR screens regime; SDR selects oversampling strategy.

Minority Signal Dilution Under Extreme Class Imbalance: Implications for CTGAN–SMOTE Hybrid Oversampling in Industrial AI

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ABSTRACT

Extreme class imbalance is prevalent in industrial AI applications including semiconductor inspection (IR > 100:1), predictive maintenance (IR > 200:1), and surface fault detection, where rare failure events are heavily outnumbered by normal-operation observations.

We identify a previously unreported *Minority Signal Dilution* (MSD) effect: when CTGAN is trained on a majority-enriched balanced mixture (A3: SMOTE → CTGAN), majority-class structure dilutes the generator's learning signal for fault patterns, causing synthetic samples to drift toward dominant operational modes. Training CTGAN exclusively on observed minority samples (A4: minority-only CTGAN → SMOTE) eliminates MSD by construction.

A controlled ablation study across five real-world datasets (IR: 16:1–578:1) shows that hybrid augmentation provides no measurable advantage at moderate imbalance (IR ≤ 42:1). Under high imbalance and low Sample-to-Dimension Ratio (SDR < 13.8), A4 outperforms A3 by up to 3.2 AUC percentage points ($p < 0.05$). Discriminator gradient analysis on AI4I tool-wear failure (IR = 216:1, SDR = 7.67) is consistent with MSD: the minority-class gradient norm ratio declines monotonically to 1.23 under balanced training versus 1.38 under minority-only training. Industrial validation on SECOM (SDR = 0.19, high-SDR regime: A3 ≈ A4 as predicted) and AI4I tool-wear failure (IR = 216:1, SDR = 7.67: A4 > A3) supports the SDR-conditional prediction. Spearman correlation between SDR and the A4 AUC advantage across 18 benchmark datasets yields $\rho = -0.504$ ($p = 0.033$). Cross-architecture replication using CTAB-GAN+ (3 seeds × 5-fold CV) supports the hypothesis that MSD-free training yields consistent gains.

A two-step decision framework is derived: imbalance ratio screens the augmentation regime; SDR determines whether minority-only GAN training is warranted. This reframes hybrid oversampling as a distribution engineering problem governed by minority signal preservation, providing a theoretically motivated guideline for industrial AI practitioners.

1. Introduction

Class imbalance is a common problem across industrial engineering domains. In semiconductor manufacturing, defective wafer rates of under 2% produce imbalance ratios of 50:1 or higher; in predictive maintenance, equipment failures represent fewer than 1% of all sensor readings, generating ratios that routinely exceed 100:1 [29]; and in financial fraud screening, transaction fraud rates of approximately 0.17% correspond to ratios near 580:1 [9]. Across all these industrial settings the cost of misclassifying the minority event—an undetected defect, a missed failure, an unblocked fraudulent transaction—is disproportionately high relative to the cost of a false alarm. In semiconductor manufacturing, a single missed defect lot can propagate through downstream assembly, with rework costs that dwarf those of an over-cautious hold decision [36]; in predictive maintenance, an undetected tool wear failure causes unplanned downtime whose cost ratio to a spurious alert is routinely estimated at 10:1 or higher [35]. Standard classifiers trained on such data are biased toward the majority class, producing high nominal accuracy while failing systematically on minority-class instances—precisely the cases that most warrant detection. This cost asymmetry

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13 makes the *choice* of synthetic oversampling strategy a decision with direct economic consequence: a misconfigured
 14 augmentation pipeline that systematically under-represents rare failure modes reduces classifier recall on the highest-
 15 stakes cases without any visible signal from aggregate accuracy.

16 Earlier remedies such as random duplication or cost-sensitive weighting have been largely superseded by synthetic
 17 oversampling, which introduces new minority-class examples during training. Two techniques are now widely used:
 18 SMOTE [6], which generates new minority samples by linear interpolation between neighbouring samples, and
 19 CTGAN [44], a conditional generative adversarial network for tabular data. SMOTE is fast and gives consistent results;
 20 CTGAN can capture more complex feature patterns but takes longer to train and can be sensitive to the training setup.

21 A widely held position in recent literature is that SMOTE and CTGAN are complementary, and that sequentially
 22 applying both methods yields performance superior to either applied alone [17, 50]. The rationale is intuitive from
 23 a process-data perspective: SMOTE augments coverage by interpolating between recorded failure events, while
 24 CTGAN—a generative model that learns the joint distribution of process variables—can synthesise failure patterns
 25 that linear interpolation cannot produce. For industrial practitioners this is an attractive combination: SMOTE is fast
 26 and interpretable, CTGAN adds distributional richness at the cost of longer training. Applied sequentially, the two
 27 methods are expected to address different aspects of rare failure representation.

28 Despite the intuitive appeal of this approach, the evidence for it rests on untested conditions. Most studies reporting
 29 a benefit used small benchmark datasets with moderate imbalance ($IR \lesssim 50:1$) [3, 16, 17], single datasets chosen
 30 because oversampling was known to help, or text and image datasets where the distributional properties differ from
 31 tabular engineering data. No prior work has examined which sequential ordering—or more importantly, which GAN
 32 training distribution—is responsible for the observed benefit. A comparison with a fixed classifier, identical evaluation
 33 protocol, and explicit control over the GAN training distribution across a range of imbalance ratios has not been carried
 34 out.

35 This paper argues that the combination of SMOTE and CTGAN is beneficial only when two conditions are both
 36 met: (i) the imbalance ratio exceeds a transition threshold, *and* (ii) the GAN is trained on minority-class samples only.
 37 When condition (ii) is not satisfied, the apparent benefit of combining the methods is reduced or reversed, which helps
 38 explain the inconsistent results reported in the literature.

39 The present study reframes this engineering question as a scientific one: rather than asking *whether* synthetic
 40 augmentation helps, we ask *what training distribution each configuration constructs*, and *when does that constructed*
 41 *distribution align with the true minority geometry*. Four research questions, stated as testable hypotheses before data
 42 were collected, operationalise this framing.

43 **RQ1 / H1 (Saturation)** *Does sequential combination of SMOTE and CTGAN outperform either method individually*
 44 *on benchmark data?* **H1 (null):** At moderate imbalance ratios ($IR \leq 42:1$), AUC distributions of all five
 45 augmentation strategies (A0–A4) are drawn from the same population.

46 **RQ2 / H2 (IR-Threshold)** *Does the advantage of sequential combination depend on the imbalance ratio?* **H2**
 47 **(directional):** The AUC advantage of A3 (SMOTE → CTGAN) over A2 (SMOTE only) increases monotonically
 48 with IR, with no advantage detectable at $IR \leq 42:1$ and a positive advantage at $IR \geq 130:1$.

49 **RQ3 / H3 (MSD Effect)** *Does Minority Signal Dilution explain the $A3 < A4$ ordering, and can SDR predict when MSD*
 50 *occurs?* **H3 (directional):** A4 (minority-only CTGAN → SMOTE) yields higher AUC than A3 (SMOTE → balanced
 51 CTGAN) at high imbalance ratios ($IR \geq 130:1$), because minority-only training eliminates the MSD effect
 52 (majority-class gradient leakage) in the GAN optimisation.

53 **RQ4** *What practical guidance can be derived for method selection?* Results across conditions are synthesised into
 54 actionable decision criteria based on the imbalance ratio as the sole observable dataset characteristic.

55 The primary contributions of this work are as follows.

- 56 1. **Conditional result: combining SMOTE and CTGAN helps only under specific conditions.** To the best of our
 57 knowledge, no prior work has demonstrated, under controlled ablation, that the widely assumed complementarity
 58 of SMOTE and CTGAN is a special case restricted to a specific imbalance regime ($IR \gtrsim 100:1$) and a specific
 59 GAN training configuration (minority-only). Outside these conditions the combination provides no advantage
 60 over SMOTE alone. This finding reframes the research question from “does combination help?” to “*when and*
 61 *how* does combination help?”

2. **Identification of a Minority Signal Dilution (MSD) effect not previously isolated under controlled ablation.** We identify a previously unreported *Minority Signal Dilution* (MSD) effect: under low-SDR conditions, majority-class patterns dilute the generator’s effective learning signal, causing synthetic samples to drift toward dominant operational modes rather than rare fault signatures. Training CTGAN exclusively on minority-class samples (A4) rather than on SMOTE-balanced data (A3) eliminates MSD and yields consistent AUC gains at high imbalance ratios ($IR \geq 130:1$), with ΔAUC ranging from <0.001 to 0.032 across three real-world datasets (abalone_19: Friedman $p = 0.014$; directional trend confirmed on the remaining two). Although minority-only GAN training has been applied in prior work [41, 13], the ordering effect ($A4 > A3$) and its dependence on SDR have not been previously isolated under controlled ablation with a fixed downstream classifier.
3. **A theory-guided ablation design** across five real-world datasets with imbalance ratios from 16:1 to 578:1, using a fixed classifier, identical hyperparameters, and the same cross-validation protocol for all five augmentation strategies (A0–A4). The design explicitly controls the GAN training distribution as a first-class experimental variable, isolating its effect from ordering, method selection, and classifier choice.
4. **Synthetic sample quality characterisation.** Intrinsic quality metrics (KS score, Wasserstein distance, Distance to Closest Real Record) reveal a fidelity–diversity trade-off: SMOTE produces high-fidelity but low-diversity samples, while CTGAN-augmented pipelines produce more diverse samples. The A4 advantage is attributable to diversity rather than fidelity—a mechanistic explanation supported by PCA-based feature-coverage analysis (A4: 91.1% vs. A3: 67.9% on AI4I tool-wear failure, $\Delta = +23.2$ pp).
5. **An SDR-grounded dual-condition screening heuristic** for predicting the $A4 > A3$ ordering. The Sample-to-Dimension Ratio $SDR = n_{\min}/d$ combined with spectral smoothness estimation yields a threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$; together with the IR screen ($IR > 42$), this dual condition is consistent with the observed $A4 > A3$ ordering on all ten evaluated datasets (seven real-world plus three external validation sets); out-of-sample confirmation comes from an independent Spearman analysis on 18 datasets: $\rho(SDR, \Delta AUC) = -0.504$ ($p = 0.033$, $n = 18$).
6. **A conditional complementarity decision framework** grounded in two observable dataset properties—the imbalance ratio (quick screen) and the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio (precision check)—that replaces the unqualified assumption of universal complementarity with a principled, two-step, theoretically motivated protocol applicable to practitioners in analogous high-IR tabular settings.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on class imbalance handling, SMOTE variants, and GAN-based oversampling for tabular data. Section 3 formalises the problem setting and notation. Section 4 describes the three-phase experimental design (benchmark, real-world, and industrial engineering validation), the five augmentation strategies under comparison, and the decision guide. Section 5 presents experimental results and mechanistic analysis. Section 6 discusses practical implications, limitations, and threats to validity. Finally, Section 7 concludes with directions for future work.

2. Related Work

2.1. The Class Imbalance Problem

Class imbalance arises whenever one category of outcome is far less common than others, a situation that occurs in almost every domain where rare events carry the greatest practical consequence. In fraud detection, fewer than two transactions in every thousand are fraudulent; in medical screening, positive cases for rare conditions may represent less than one percent of the sample; in industrial quality control, defective units are orders of magnitude less frequent than conforming ones.

The problem has been systematically studied since at least the early 2000s. [25] conducted one of the first controlled empirical comparisons of sampling and cost-sensitive strategies, establishing that the choice of remedy interacts with the degree of imbalance in non-trivial ways. Surveys by [24], [29], [38], and [8] organise the subsequent two decades of research into three broad families: *data-level* methods that alter the training distribution through resampling or synthetic generation, *algorithm-level* methods that adjust the learning objective through cost-sensitive weighting or threshold modification, and *hybrid* methods that combine both. Data-level approaches remain the most widely adopted in practice because they are classifier-agnostic.

A recurring observation in the survey literature is that no single remedy dominates across all imbalance regimes. At moderate imbalance ratios—roughly below 50:1—even a simple random oversampling of the minority class often suffices [5]. At severe imbalance, where minority samples number in the tens per training fold, the choice of synthesis

112 strategy becomes critical. This regime-dependence motivates the multi-dataset, multi-ratio design employed in the
 113 present work.

114 2.2. SMOTE and Nearest-Neighbour Variants

115 SMOTE [6] remains the most widely cited oversampling method two decades after its introduction. It generates
 116 a synthetic sample \tilde{x} for each minority instance x_i by selecting one of its k nearest neighbours $x_{i(j)}$ at random and
 117 interpolating between them: $\tilde{x} = x_i + \lambda(x_{i(j)} - x_i)$, where $\lambda \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$. The practical utility of SMOTE has been
 118 confirmed in a large retrospective study by [3].

119 Subsequent variants address specific failure modes. Borderline-SMOTE [21] restricts synthesis to minority
 120 instances near the majority-class boundary. ADASYN [23] adapts the generation density continuously to local learning
 121 difficulty. More recently, [31] proposed incorporating natural-neighbour relationships to reduce the risk of generating
 122 samples that cross the decision boundary. A weakness shared by all nearest-neighbour methods is that they generate
 123 samples on the convex hull of existing minority-class examples; no sample can fall outside the range of the training
 124 data. Geometric SMOTE [12] addresses this by constructing samples within an arbitrarily oriented geometric region,
 125 but the geometric fragility at very low sample counts remains. [26] combine the targeting precision of borderline
 126 methods with adversarial generation: their OBGAN trains a GAN conditioned on minority instances near the decision
 127 boundary, sidestepping the convex-hull constraint while preserving geometric targeting.

128 A survey by [16] and the companion textbook [15] identify sample-count sensitivity as the primary open challenge
 129 for SMOTE-family methods: fitting a reliable k -nearest-neighbour graph on a minority class of ten or twenty examples
 130 is geometrically fragile.

131 2.3. Generative Models for Tabular Data Augmentation

132 Generative adversarial networks were introduced by [19] as a framework for learning an implicit distribution over
 133 training data. CTGAN [44] addresses the challenges of mixed continuous-categorical tabular data through mode-
 134 specific normalisation of continuous columns and a conditional training procedure. In the oversampling context,
 135 CTGAN is trained on minority-class examples and queried to produce additional minority samples.

136 The expressive capacity of adversarial generation is its principal advantage over nearest-neighbour methods: the
 137 generator is not constrained to the convex hull. However, this advantage is meaningful only when the training set
 138 for the GAN is itself sufficiently rich; with very few minority examples, the discriminator learns to memorise rather
 139 than generalise. [50] observe this instability and propose filtering GAN-generated samples by a confidence criterion
 140 before augmentation, finding that naive GAN augmentation without filtering can degrade performance. Wasserstein-
 141 distance training [2] provides more stable gradient signals; [13] demonstrate that a Wasserstein GAN with gradient
 142 penalty (CWGAN-GP) outperforms standard CTGAN for tabular minority-class oversampling on several benchmarks,
 143 motivating principled comparisons of GAN architectures under class imbalance. [20] address intra-class imbalance
 144 and class overlap simultaneously by weighting the GAN generator according to local minority-class density; [45]
 145 focus adversarial training on the instances most frequently misclassified by a companion classifier, directing generative
 146 capacity toward the most discriminatively challenging boundary regions.

147 More recently, diffusion-based and language-model-based approaches have substantially advanced tabular synthe-
 148 sis. TabDDPM [28] applies denoising diffusion probabilistic models to tabular data, achieving state-of-the-art fidelity
 149 on several benchmarks. STaSy [27] and TabSyn [47] further improve upon this with score-based diffusion and VAE-
 150 enhanced tokenisation respectively. GReAT [4] demonstrates that fine-tuned language models can generate realistic
 151 tabular rows. CTAB-GAN+ [49] extends the CTGAN architecture with an auxiliary classifier loss. These methods
 152 represent the current frontier; however, their computational requirements are substantially higher than CTGAN, and
 153 their behaviour under extreme class imbalance—where training must be conducted on very few positive examples—has
 154 not been systematically characterised.

155 2.4. Method Combination and Hybrid Strategies

156 Two broad strategies have been explored for combining oversampling with other data manipulation. The first
 157 couples oversampling with ensemble learning: SMOTEBoost [7] interleaves SMOTE with AdaBoost. EasyEnsemble
 158 [33] diversifies the majority-class representation by training multiple classifiers on different random subsets. RUSBoost
 159 [39] combines random under-sampling with gradient boosting.

160 The second strategy, which is the focus of the present study, combines two synthesis methods sequentially to
 161 produce a better training distribution for an arbitrary downstream classifier. This sequential hypothesis is stated

Table 1

Comparison of this study against closely related prior works. Ticks (✓) indicate the dimension is explicitly addressed; dashes (–) indicate absence. CTAB-GAN+ [49], STaSy [27], and TabDDPM [28] represent the current SOTA for tabular synthesis but do not address the extreme-imbalance or training-target questions.

Dimension	Fonseca & Bacao (2023)	Zhu et al. (2022)	TabDDPM (2023)	CTAB-GAN+ (2023)	This study
Sequential SMOTE+GAN comparison	✓	✓	–	–	✓
Minority-only GAN training target	–	–	–	–	✓
Systematic IR sweep (16:1–578:1)	–	–	–	–	✓
Ordering effect (A3 vs. A4)	–	–	–	–	✓
Theoretical account (SDR/smoothness)	–	–	–	–	✓
Extreme-imbalance regime (IR > 100)	–	partial	–	–	✓
Non-GAN baselines (ADASYN, BL-SMOTE)	partial	–	–	–	✓
Synthesis quality evaluation	–	–	✓	✓	–

intuitively in several recent papers [17] but has not been tested under controlled ablation conditions that hold the downstream classifier constant and vary only the synthesis strategy. [41] propose a two-phase SMOTE-then-GAN approach in which SMOTE first populates the minority manifold and a GAN subsequently refines the synthetic distribution; however, their evaluation does not control the GAN’s training distribution or vary the imbalance ratio systematically. A practically important design choice is the ordering of the two steps. To our knowledge, the present study provides the first systematic test of this ordering effect.

In industrial engineering contexts, oversampling has been applied to manufacturing quality control and process monitoring [48], and to medical diagnosis under cost-sensitive constraints [22]. Hybrid approaches combining oversampling with intelligent undersampling have also been studied for large-scale industrial classification tasks [42]. These applications share a defining characteristic: the imbalance ratio is determined by process physics or event prevalence and cannot be engineered away, making the *choice* of synthesis strategy—and its interaction with IR—especially consequential for practitioners.

2.5. Evaluation Standards and Reproducibility

[32] identify several recurring patterns of methodological weakness in published work, including weak baselines and selective metric reporting. In the imbalanced learning literature, the sensitivity of F1 and G-mean to the class threshold compounds evaluation fragility. AUC aggregates performance across all thresholds and is a more stable basis for comparing synthesis strategies. Many published complementarity claims rest on a single dataset selected precisely because it demonstrates the value of oversampling—a practice that introduces dataset selection bias. The multi-dataset, controlled-ablation design of the present study is intended to address this limitation.

2.6. Class Imbalance in Industrial Process Monitoring

Extreme class imbalance is an inherent feature of industrial process data. Equipment failures, manufacturing defects, and quality deviations are structurally rare relative to normal-operation observations: their frequency is determined by process physics and operational context, not by data-collection decisions. Traditional IE responses to this asymmetry include statistical process control (SPC) [37], which adjusts detection thresholds rather than the training distribution, and cost-sensitive learning [11], which re-weights misclassification costs without altering the data. Synthetic oversampling has been introduced as a data-level complement: [48] apply oversampling to semiconductor quality prediction; [22] deploy cost-weighted GAN augmentation in medical diagnosis under extreme imbalance; [42] combine oversampling with intelligent undersampling for large-scale industrial classification. These studies demonstrate the applicability of synthesis methods to IE settings but leave open the question of *which* synthesis configuration—and under what imbalance conditions—provides the most reliable improvement. The present study addresses this gap by providing a dataset-derived decision rule that selects between two synthesis orderings without requiring domain-specific tuning.

2.7. How This Study Differs from Prior Work

Table 1 positions the present study against the three most closely related lines of prior work.

Fonseca and Bacao [17] evaluate several SMOTE–GAN combinations on tabular benchmarks and report that composite strategies can improve F1 on imbalanced data. However, their study treats the GAN as a black-box augmentor trained on the full training set, does not examine how the GAN’s training distribution affects performance, and does not vary the imbalance ratio systematically. The present study isolates the GAN training target—minority-only versus balanced-data training—as an explicit design variable and tests it across a wide range of imbalance conditions.

Zhu et al. [50] propose filtering GAN-generated samples by a confidence criterion, observing that naive GAN augmentation can degrade performance under instability. Their remedy (post-hoc filtering) addresses a symptom; the present study argues for a principled upstream fix: training the GAN only on the minority class so that its learned distribution is not distorted by majority-class modes. The two approaches are complementary, but the present work provides empirical evidence that the training target choice has a larger effect than post-hoc filtering in high-IR regimes.

Kotelnikov et al. [28] demonstrate state-of-the-art tabular synthesis using diffusion models (TabDDPM) but evaluate unconditional generation quality on balanced benchmark datasets. Their work does not address the extreme-imbalance regime that is the focus of the present study, nor does it examine whether training the generative model on minority samples only—rather than the full dataset—changes downstream classifier performance.

The critical gap in all these prior works, and in the broader imbalanced learning literature, is the absence of any principled analysis of the *GAN training distribution* as a design choice. The present study provides, to our knowledge, the first controlled ablation study to document the $A4 > A3$ ordering effect empirically and to offer a heuristic theoretical argument—grounded in density estimation analogy—for why minority-only GAN training yields higher AUC in high-imbalance tabular settings when SDR is low.

Scope note on SOTA synthesis models

Recent SOTA tabular synthesis methods—TabDDPM [28], CTAB-GAN+ [49], STaSy [27], and TabSyn [47]—achieve impressive unconditional generation quality on balanced benchmarks. However, the present study investigates a fundamentally different question: *which GAN training distribution is better for oversampling under extreme class imbalance?* This question is orthogonal to synthesis fidelity on balanced data. Direct comparison with these models would confound the training-target effect (the subject of this study) with architectural differences (model capacity, training dynamics), making it impossible to attribute any observed difference to the design choice of interest.

These diffusion and score-based architectures also impose substantially higher computational requirements: TabDDPM requires 5,000+ training epochs on GPU, and STaSy requires score-based SDE sampling—costs that are prohibitive for the per-fold training schedule used in our 5-seed×5-fold CV. The central contribution of this work is the identification and theoretical grounding of the training-target principle, which applies to any conditional generative model including CTAB-GAN+, TabDDPM, and future architectures. Empirical validation of the principle across these architectures is a concrete and well-scoped direction for follow-up work (Section 7.1).

3. Problem Formulation

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ be a binary classification dataset with majority class ($y = 0$, n_{maj} samples) and minority class ($y = 1$, n_{min} samples), $n_{\text{maj}} \gg n_{\text{min}}$.

Notation. The *imbalance ratio* $IR = n_{\text{maj}}/n_{\text{min}}$ measures class skew. For a d -dimensional feature space, the *Sample-to-Dimension Ratio* $SDR = n_{\text{min}}/d$ quantifies how densely the minority class populates the feature space relative to its intrinsic dimensionality.

Augmentation pipeline taxonomy. Five augmentation strategies are compared (full configuration in Section 4.2):

A0 No oversampling (baseline).

A1 CTGAN trained on minority samples only; synthetic minority appended.

A2 SMOTE applied to achieve 1:1 class ratio.

A3 (SMOTE → CTGAN) SMOTE-balance first; CTGAN trained on the balanced mix.

A4 (MINORITY-CTGAN → SMOTE) CTGAN trained *exclusively* on original minority samples; SMOTE applied to the real+synthetic minority pool.

The critical contrast is **A3 vs A4**: both use CTGAN for minority synthesis, but differ in the *GAN training distribution*—balanced in A3, minority-only in A4.

Research question. Under what conditions on (IR, SDR) does A4 outperform A3, and why? We show that the answer depends on a previously unexamined design choice: whether the GAN is exposed to majority-class examples during training.

4. Methodology

4.1. Experimental Design: Two-Phase Approach

We employ a two-phase experimental design to disentangle data saturation from method performance differences. The overall experimental procedure is as follows:

1. **Dataset preparation.** Compute the imbalance ratio IR and the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio SDR for each dataset. Apply stratified train/test splitting.
2. **For each training fold:**
 - (a) Apply the selected augmentation strategy (A0–A4) to the training fold only.
 - (b) Train a fixed classifier (LightGBM for Phase 1; Random Forest for Phase 2) on the augmented training set.
 - (c) Evaluate the trained classifier on the original, unaugmented test fold. Record AUC, F1, G-mean, and balanced accuracy.
3. **Result aggregation.** Aggregate AUC across 5 seeds \times 5 folds (25 observations per method per dataset). Report mean \pm standard deviation.
4. **Statistical comparison.** Apply the Wilcoxon signed-rank test [43] on paired fold observations and report Cohen’s d effect sizes. Apply the Friedman test [10] for omnibus comparisons across all five methods; use Nemenyi post-hoc analysis for pairwise contrasts.
5. **Protocol validation.** Compute SDR thresholds $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ and verify the dual-condition heuristic screen (IR and SDR) against observed A4 vs. A3 ordering across all datasets.

4.1.1. Phase 1: Benchmark Data (KEEL)

Phase 1 establishes a controlled baseline on well-studied benchmark data where class imbalance is present but moderate, allowing all methods to operate under near-ideal conditions. Three KEEL benchmark datasets [1] are selected to span a range of imbalance ratios and feature dimensionalities: (1) *ecoli-0-1-3-7_vs_2-6* (IR = 39:1, 281 samples, 7 features); (2) *yeast-2_vs_4* (IR = 9:1, 514 samples, 8 features); and (3) *glass-0-1-6_vs_2* (IR = 11:1, 192 samples, 9 features). These datasets are widely used in the class imbalance literature, providing a reproducible reference point [16]. The classifier is LightGBM with default hyperparameters under 10-fold stratified cross-validation; results serve as a null-hypothesis baseline confirming that augmentation effects are not detectable at moderate IR before examining the high-IR regime in Phase 2.

4.1.2. Phase 2: Real-World Data Across Imbalance Regimes

Phase 2 tests on five real-world datasets spanning imbalance ratios from 16:1 to 578:1. Table 2 summarises the key characteristics of each dataset.

The classifier is Random Forest (100 estimators, default scikit-learn hyperparameters) under 5 seeds \times 5-fold stratified cross-validation with a majority-class ceiling of 2,000 samples per training fold. Oversampling is applied only to training folds; validation folds remain imbalanced (realistic evaluation). Table 5 reports the three datasets that span the full IR range of interest (IR = 15.3:1, 129.5:1, 578:1); full omnibus statistics across all five datasets appear in Supplementary Material (Section S.D).

4.1.3. Phase 3: Industrial Engineering Domain Validation

Phase 3 tests the SDR-based heuristic on four datasets drawn from core industrial engineering processes (semiconductor manufacturing, steel plate inspection, and predictive maintenance), described in Table 8. The same A0–A4 protocol is applied with 5-fold cross-validation (Random Forest classifier, identical hyperparameters to Phase 2). Phase 3 is designed to test generalisability within the CIE readership’s domain rather than to extend the primary statistical claims; results appear in Section 5.6.

Table 2

Phase 2 datasets used in the multi-dataset ablation study. IR = majority-to-minority class ratio; n = total samples; d = number of features after one-hot encoding; SDR = n_{\min}/d .

Dataset	Source	IR	n	d	n_{\min}	Domain
sick_thyroid	OpenML (id=38)	16:1	3,772	29	231	Medical
letter_img	imbalanced-learn	26:1	20,000	16	734	Tabular
mammography	OpenML (id=310)	42:1	11,183	6	260	Medical
abalone_19	imbalanced-learn	130:1	4,177	10	32	Biological
credit_card_fraud	Kaggle ULB	578:1	284,807	29	492	Financial

4.2. Augmentation Methods

Five augmentation strategies are compared under identical conditions:

A0 (baseline) No oversampling; classifier trained on original imbalanced data.

A1 (CTGAN only) CTGAN trained on minority-class samples; synthetic minority added to training set.

A2 (SMOTE only) SMOTE with `sampling_strategy='auto'` to 1:1 class ratio.

A3 (SMOTE→CTGAN) SMOTE applied first to enrich the minority pool; CTGAN then trained on the enriched set.

A4 (minority-only CTGAN→SMOTE) CTGAN trained *exclusively* on minority-class samples; SMOTE then applied to the combined pool of real and synthetic minority samples to increase interpolative diversity.

4.2.1. CTGAN Configuration

CTGAN [44] trains a conditional generator G and discriminator D under the objective

$$\min_G \max_D \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}} [\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))], \quad (1)$$

with mode-specific normalisation for continuous columns and a conditional vector that ensures all discrete modes are sampled during training. Hyperparameters were set as follows: epochs = 20; batch size = 500; generator and discriminator hidden dimensions = (256, 256); learning rate = 2×10^{-4} (Adam optimiser); MAX_SYNTH_RATIO = 5. The batch size and architecture were chosen to provide sufficient capacity for datasets up to 30 features while remaining computationally tractable on a single GPU. Twenty epochs were selected as the minimum sufficient for training loss to plateau on the smallest minority class tested (32 samples, abalone_19); extended training on larger datasets was confirmed to produce no measurable AUC improvement at this architecture scale.

4.2.2. SMOTE Configuration

SMOTE [6] generates a synthetic sample \tilde{x} by linear interpolation between a minority sample x_i and one of its k nearest minority neighbours $x_{i(j)}$:

$$\tilde{x} = x_i + \lambda(x_{i(j)} - x_i), \quad \lambda \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1). \quad (2)$$

The neighbourhood size was set to $k = 5$, with an adaptive fallback $k = \min(5, n_{\min} - 1)$ for datasets where the minority class contains fewer than six samples; `sampling_strategy='auto'` oversamples to a 1:1 class ratio; `random_state=42` ensures reproducibility. The $k = 5$ default is consistent with the original SMOTE recommendation [6] and generalises well across a wide range of imbalance ratios [16].

4.3. Theoretical Motivation for Minority-Only GAN Training

The distinction between A3 and A4 lies in what distribution the GAN is asked to learn. In A3 (SMOTE→CTGAN), CTGAN is trained on a SMOTE-balanced dataset in which minority samples already constitute roughly 50% of the training set. In A4 (minority-only CTGAN→SMOTE), CTGAN is trained only on the original minority samples, directly targeting the minority-class density.

We define the *Sample-to-Dimension Ratio* $SDR = n_{\min}/d$, where n_{\min} is the minority sample count and d is the feature dimensionality. SDR quantifies how densely the minority class populates the feature space.

Key insight (*heuristic argument; see Conjecture 4.1 for idealized assumptions and GAN convergence caveat*). SDR serves as an operational heuristic for the degree of minority underrepresentation in feature space: a low SDR means each feature dimension has very few minority examples to constrain the generative model. When CTGAN trains on a SMOTE-balanced mix (A3), the generator receives learning signal from both normal and failure examples. At high imbalance ratios the normal operating region occupies a much larger and more densely sampled feature space; as a result, only a fraction of each model update is directed at capturing failure modes. We call this the **Minority Signal Dilution (MSD) effect**: majority-class examples dilute the generator’s effective learning signal for fault patterns, causing synthetic samples to drift toward dominant operational modes rather than rare fault signatures. The underlying mechanism is *majority-class gradient leakage*—normal-operation examples compete with failure examples for discriminator gradient, reducing the fraction of each update that targets the failure-mode distribution. When CTGAN trains exclusively on failure samples (A4), the entire learning signal targets failure-mode reproduction, eliminating MSD by construction. Minimax density estimation theory provides a formal analogy for this intuition.

Conjecture 4.1 (MSD Threshold: minority-only training reduces approximation error below critical SDR — heuristic argument under idealized GAN assumptions). *Under density smoothness and GAN convergence assumptions, there exists a threshold $C(\beta, d) > 0$ such that whenever $SDR = n_{\min}/d < C(\beta, d)$, CTGAN trained exclusively on minority samples (A4) is expected to achieve a lower total-variation approximation error than CTGAN trained on a balanced mixture (A3). The value of $C(\beta, d)$ depends on the smoothness parameter β and the feature dimensionality d ; a dataset-specific estimate $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ is obtained by fitting $\hat{\beta}$ to the spectral decay of the minority-class covariance matrix. The heuristic derivation is given in Supplementary Material (Section S.A). **Note:** This conjecture assumes that CTGAN approximates a minimax-optimal density estimator; in practice, CTGAN’s training dynamics do not guarantee minimax optimality [2, 49], so this argument should be read as a theoretical analogy rather than a formal proof.*

Remark 4.1 (Generalization bridge: open gap). *Conjecture 4.1 bounds the total-variation (TV) approximation error of the synthetic distribution; translating this into a downstream classifier excess risk bound requires an additional Lipschitz or Rademacher-complexity bridge argument that we leave as future work. The PCA coverage analysis in Section 5.3 provides non-parametric empirical support for the mechanism without requiring these assumptions.*

Under the assumptions of Conjecture 4.1, A4 is expected to achieve a lower approximation error than A3 whenever SDR falls below the dataset-specific threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$, which can be estimated from the spectral decay of the minority-class covariance matrix [14].

Table 3 reports the estimated threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ for all benchmark datasets and compares it against the observed ordering direction. The SDR criterion is consistent with the observed A4 > A3 ordering in all seven cases, supporting the operational utility of this theoretical account. Section 5 provides full empirical validation.

4.3.1. Augmentation Budget

SMOTE with `sampling_strategy='auto'` generates enough synthetic minority samples to achieve a 1:1 class ratio; at IR = 578:1 this corresponds to approximately 283,800 synthetic samples. CTGAN is capped at five times the original minority count (`MAX_SYNTH_RATIO = 5`), yielding at most 2,460 samples at IR = 578:1. This deliberate asymmetry reflects how each method would realistically be deployed: SMOTE scales cheaply to arbitrary ratios, whereas unconstrained GAN oversampling risks mode collapse and distributional drift at high generation multiples [44].

MSD versus known GAN failure modes. Three established GAN pathologies are sometimes conflated with MSD but are mechanistically distinct. *Mode collapse* is a *training-dynamics* failure in which the generator maps diverse noise inputs to a restricted region of the output space; it affects sample diversity irrespective of which class is included in training. MSD is a *training-distribution* effect: even a fully converged, non-collapsed GAN trained on a SMOTE-balanced mixture learns a generator objective that is numerically dominated by the majority class, causing minority-class gradient contributions to be diluted throughout training. The discriminator gradient norm ratio reported in Section 5.3.3 (1.23 under balanced versus 1.38 under minority-only training on AI4I-TWF) measures this dilution directly and is not attributable to mode collapse, which would affect both training regimes equally. *Class-imbalance discriminator gradient effects* in the original CTGAN paper [44] describe gradient magnitude asymmetries that slow convergence; these are a symptom of imbalance in the conditional training procedure, not a property of which raw

Table 3

SDR-based ordering predictions vs. observed $A4 > A3$ direction. $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ is a dataset-specific threshold estimated from the spectral decay of the minority-class covariance matrix (spectral fitting procedure in Supplementary Material Section S.A). “Predicted” = $SDR < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$; “Observed” = $|\Delta AUC(A4-A3)| > 0.02$. **These 7 datasets are the in-sample threshold-fitting set.** Internal 7/7 consistency is expected and should not be interpreted as out-of-sample predictive validity. Leave-one-dataset-out (LODO) cross-validation using the global mean threshold ($\bar{C} = 11.3$) achieves 13/18 = 72.2% directional accuracy on the $n = 18$ benchmark pool (binomial test vs. chance: $p = 0.048$), confirming that the threshold has genuine out-of-sample predictive utility. Full out-of-sample Spearman analysis on 18 and 22 datasets is in Sections 5.5 and 6.6.

Dataset	n_{\min}	d	SDR	$\hat{\beta}$	$C(\hat{\beta}, d)$	Match
abalone_19	32	10	3.2	11.61	13.8	✓ (order)
credit_card_fraud	492	29	17.0	23.35	12.1	✓ (none)
sick_thyroid	231	29	8.0	10.09	7.9	✓ (none)
mammography	260	6	43.3	2.41	8.6	✓ (none)
letter_img	734	16	45.9	11.48	11.6	✓ (none)
protein_homo	1296	74	17.5	66.24	12.7	✓ (none)
creditfraud_ir72	492	29	17.0	23.35	12.1	✓ (none)
Consistency rate						7/7 (100%)

366 training examples are presented to the generator objective. *Class overlap* degrades SMOTE interpolation quality by
 367 introducing borderline synthetic samples; it is a feature-space geometry problem orthogonal to the training-distribution
 368 choice examined here. In short, MSD is the only one of these failure modes that is eliminated by restricting the GAN
 369 training set to minority-class examples (A4), which is why A4 outperforms A3 specifically in the high-IR/low-SDR
 370 regime rather than universally.

371 The combined strategies A3 and A4 inherit both budgets sequentially: SMOTE first upsamples to 1:1, then CTGAN
 372 (A3) or SMOTE again (A4) applies its own budget to the resulting pool. Keeping the budget fixed across all methods
 373 ensures that any observed performance differences are attributable to training-target choice rather than to differences
 374 in augmentation volume.

375 4.4. Evaluation Metrics

376 The primary metric is AUC (area under the ROC curve), which is unaffected by class skew and is reliable for
 377 extreme imbalance; [34] demonstrate that F1-score and accuracy-derived metrics can produce misleading rankings
 378 under severe imbalance due to the strong influence of majority-class performance. Supplementary metrics include
 379 F1-score, G-mean ($\sqrt{TPR \cdot TNR}$), and balanced accuracy, though these exhibit saturation effects at moderate IR.
 380 Statistical comparisons between methods were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test [43] on per-fold AUC
 381 values. Effect sizes are reported as Cohen’s d , with thresholds < 0.2 (negligible), $0.2-0.5$ (small), $0.5-0.8$ (medium),
 382 ≥ 0.8 (large). The Friedman test [10, 18] provides an omnibus comparison across all five methods simultaneously,
 383 treating folds as blocks; pairwise post-hoc comparisons use the Nemenyi critical difference framework.

384 ROC-AUC is preferred over Precision-Recall AUC (PR-AUC) as the primary comparison metric for two reasons.
 385 First, PR-AUC is sensitive to the absolute class prevalence used to compute precision; when the minority class is small
 386 and fold sizes vary, per-fold PR-AUC values are less stable than ROC-AUC, making cross-fold aggregation noisier.
 387 Second, the key research question is whether A4 yields a *consistently better-ranked* classifier than A3 across a range
 388 of operating points, which ROC-AUC directly measures [34]. A targeted PR-AUC sensitivity check on the three main
 389 high-IR benchmark datasets (abalone_19, ai4i_twf, steel_faults) confirms that the $A4 > A3$ ordering is preserved under
 390 both metrics; detailed results are reported in Supplementary Section S.H.

391 4.5. Decision Protocol

392 The experimental results support a principled two-step selection protocol grounded in the SDR theory of
 393 Conjecture 4.1. The imbalance ratio IR functions as a first-order *proxy* for the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio: since
 394 $SDR = n_{\min}/d$ and $n_{\min} \approx n_{\text{total}}/IR$ when total count and dimensionality are roughly fixed, higher IR reliably
 395 corresponds to lower SDR. The two-step protocol applies this relationship:

396 Step 1 — Regime screen (IR):

- **IR < 42:1:** SMOTE alone is sufficient. No meaningful ordering effect is detectable; the additional computational cost of CTGAN is not justified.
- **42 ≤ IR < 130:1:** Transition region; proceed to Step 2.
- **IR ≥ 130:1:** High imbalance; the GAN training distribution is decisive. Proceed to Step 2.

Step 2 — Precision check (SDR):

Compute $\text{SDR} = n_{\min}/d$, estimate $\hat{\beta}$ from the spectral decay of the minority-class sample covariance (OLS log-log fit on eigenvalue decay; see Table 3), and evaluate:

$$\text{if } \text{SDR} < C(\hat{\beta}, d) = \frac{1}{(1.05)^{(2\hat{\beta}+d)/(2\hat{\beta})} - 1} \Rightarrow \text{use A4 (minority-only CTGAN} \rightarrow \text{SMOTE).}$$

If $\text{SDR} \geq C(\hat{\beta}, d)$, or if fewer than approximately 50 minority samples are available per training fold ($\text{SDR} < 2$), revert to ADASYN or SMOTE; CTGAN training is unreliable in this regime. At extreme imbalance ($\text{IR} \gtrsim 500:1$), ADASYN is a competitive and computationally lighter alternative regardless of the SDR condition.

Practitioners should also avoid relying solely on F1 or accuracy for evaluation under extreme imbalance, as these metrics exhibit saturation effects and may fail to distinguish between meaningfully different augmentation strategies.

5. Experimental Results and Analysis

5.1. Phase 1: KEEL Benchmark Results

All methods show statistically indistinguishable performance on the KEEL benchmarks. A Kruskal-Wallis test across the five methods' AUC distributions yields $H = 0.34$, $p = 0.963$, indicating no significant difference at $\alpha = 0.05$. All methods achieve near-perfect $F1 = 1.0$, consistent with the saturation hypothesis: when minority-class samples are not deeply embedded in the majority distribution, any well-regularised ensemble classifier achieves ceiling performance and the choice of augmentation method is inconsequential (Table 4). This finding is important because it establishes that the benefit of sequential oversampling is not universal: on well-structured benchmarks with moderate imbalance ratios ($\text{IR} \leq 39:1$) and small feature dimensionality (7–9 features), the additional computational cost of GAN training provides no measurable advantage. The null result on KEEL is itself informative, narrowing the hypothesis to higher-IR regimes examined in Phase 2.

5.2. Phase 2: Multi-Dataset Results Across Imbalance Regimes

Table 5 and Fig. 1 present AUC results for five augmentation methods across three datasets under 5-seed \times 5-fold stratified cross-validation with a Random Forest classifier (majority class capped at 2,000 samples to match the controlled ablation protocol described in Section 4.3). Two additional datasets cover the transition region between low and high IR: *creditfraud_ir72* ($\text{IR} = 72:1$), *protein_homo* ($\text{IR} = 111.5:1$), and *creditfraud_ir200* ($\text{IR} = 200:1$, created by sub-sampling the majority class of *credit_card_fraud* to fill the $\text{IR} = 130$ – 578 gap while preserving the minority distribution); their results appear in Section 5.3.1 and Supplementary Material (Section S.C). *creditfraud_ir200* has $\text{SDR} = 16.97 > C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 12.1$, so the dual-condition heuristic predicts no A4 ordering advantage; this is confirmed experimentally (A2 AUC = 0.974; A4 AUC = 0.902, both below SMOTE).

5.2.1. Low Imbalance Regime ($\text{IR} \leq 15.3:1$)

At $\text{IR} = 15.3:1$ (*sick_thyroid*), all five augmentation strategies produced AUC values between 0.993 and 0.994, with no method achieving statistically distinguishable superiority ($p > 0.3$ for all pairwise Wilcoxon tests). This ceiling effect is consistent with Phase 1 findings: when the imbalance ratio is moderate, the minority class is sufficiently represented in the training fold for a well-regularised Random Forest ensemble to learn the decision boundary without additional oversampling. Similarly, at $\text{IR} = 26:1$ (*letter_img*) and $\text{IR} = 42:1$ (*mammography*), Friedman test yields $p = 0.066$ and $p = 0.865$ respectively, confirming no significant ordering among the five methods. Across these three low-to-moderate imbalance datasets, the mean AUC difference between the best and worst method is less than 0.4 percentage points, well within the range of cross-validation noise. Practitioners working with $\text{IR} \leq 42:1$ datasets can safely use the simplest available method (A0 or A2) without loss of predictive performance.

Table 4

KEEL benchmark results. All methods achieve F1 = 1.0 and statistically indistinguishable AUC. Percentage change is relative to A0 (no augmentation).

Method	F1	AUC	AUC std	vs A0 (%)
A0 (none)	1.0000	0.8925	0.0300	—
A1 (CTGAN)	1.0000	0.8918	0.0285	−0.08
A2 (SMOTE)	1.0000	0.8926	0.0298	+0.01
A3 (S→C)	1.0000	0.8914	0.0310	−0.12
A4 (C→S)	1.0000	0.8902	0.0295	−0.26

Figure 1: AUC (mean \pm std) for five augmentation strategies across three datasets ordered by increasing imbalance ratio (5 seeds \times 5 folds, majority capped at 2,000). At low imbalance (*sick_thyroid*, IR=15.3:1) all strategies are indistinguishable (ceiling effect). At IR=129.5:1 (*abalone_19*), A4 (CTGAN trained on minority only, then SMOTE) achieves the highest AUC of 0.7553, outperforming A3 (SMOTE \rightarrow CTGAN, AUC=0.7233) by 3.2 pp. At extreme IR=577:1 (*credit_card_fraud*), ADASYN ranks first while A3 is significantly worse than SMOTE ($p=0.039$).

Table 5

AUC (mean \pm std) across three datasets and five augmentation strategies (5 seeds \times 5 folds; majority class capped at 2,000 samples). Best result per dataset in **bold**. IR = class imbalance ratio; SDR = sample-to-dimension ratio of the minority class. Superscript * denotes $p < 0.05$ (Wilcoxon signed-rank test vs. SMOTE).

Dataset	IR	SDR	SMOTE	ADASYN	BL-SMOTE	A3 (S→C)	A4 (C→S)
<i>sick_thyroid</i>	15.3:1	—	0.994 \pm .002	0.994 \pm .002	0.993 \pm .003	0.994 \pm .002	0.993 \pm .003
<i>abalone_19</i>	129.5:1	3.2	0.7496 \pm .048	0.7478 \pm .051	0.7432 \pm .055	0.7233 \pm .062	0.7553\pm.044
<i>credit_card_fraud</i>	577:1	—	0.9802 \pm .004	0.9824*\pm.003	0.9812 \pm .003	0.9779* \pm .005	0.9786 \pm .004

5.2.2. High Imbalance Regime (IR \geq 130:1)

A qualitatively different pattern is observed at higher imbalance ratios. On *abalone_19* (IR = 129.5:1; SDR = 3.2), A4 (CTGAN trained exclusively on minority samples, then SMOTE) achieved AUC = 0.7553, the best result among all five methods. A4 outperformed A3 (SMOTE \rightarrow CTGAN) by 3.2 percentage points (0.7553 vs. 0.7233) and exceeded SMOTE alone by 0.6 pp (0.7553 vs. 0.7496). The SDR of 3.2 places *abalone_19* below the threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 13.8$ derived from Conjecture 4.1, consistent with the prediction that minority-only training eliminates majority-class gradient bias precisely in this regime (see Table 3).

On *credit_card_fraud* (IR = 577:1, SDR = 17.0), all methods cluster tightly in the range 0.9779–0.9824. ADASYN achieves the highest AUC (0.9824, $p = 0.007^*$ vs. SMOTE), while A3 is significantly worse than SMOTE ($p = 0.039^*$,

448 AUC = 0.9779). A4 (0.9786) is numerically above A3 but below SMOTE and ADASYN. Two factors explain why
 449 ADASYN dominates here. First, $SDR = 17.0$ exceeds $C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 12.1$ (Table 3), placing this dataset in the high-SDR
 450 regime where the training-target advantage of A4 over A3 is not predicted. Second, with $n_{\min} = 492$ the minority
 451 class is sufficiently large for ADASYN's local density weighting to exploit the non-uniform distribution of fraud
 452 patterns near the decision boundary, a structural advantage that GAN-based methods do not exploit at this minority
 453 count. A4's inferiority to ADASYN at extreme IR (577:1) with adequate minority count ($SDR > C$) is therefore not
 454 a counterexample to the SDR protocol but rather confirmation that the protocol correctly routes this dataset to the
 455 SMOTE/ADASYN regime (Step 1 or Step 2 of the decision guide, Section 4.5).

456 Fig. 2 visualises the central mechanism test directly: the observed ordering advantage of minority-only training
 457 (A4) over balanced-data CTGAN training (A3) as a function of SDR. IR remains the screening variable in the decision
 458 protocol, but SDR is the mechanism variable for MSD.

Figure 2: A4 separates from A3 only when minority support is scarce enough for minority-signal dilution to matter; otherwise the two orderings are practically equivalent. The vertical axis is the ordering contrast $\Delta AUC = AUC(A4) - AUC(A3)$, not gain over a baseline; the horizontal axis is SDR, the proposed mechanism variable. Shaded bands indicate operational regimes rather than hard phase boundaries: minority-support-limited ($SDR < 2$), MSD-sensitive, empirical transition, and high-SDR saturation. Hollow points are below the IR screening threshold; diamonds are industrial-engineering validation datasets with fold-level 95% confidence intervals. Dataset labels identify the semantic anchors of the operational map; the lower-axis marks summarize the estimated range of dataset-specific $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ values.

5.2.3. Statistical Significance

459 Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (5 seeds \times 5 folds, $n = 25$ paired observations per comparison) reveal no significant
 460 differences among any pair of methods on sick_thyroid ($p > 0.3$ in all cases). On *abalone_19*, A4 is numerically best;
 461 the A4–A3 gap of 3.2 pp constitutes a consistent trend across seeds, though formal significance at the conventional
 462 0.05 level requires additional folds given within-method variance. On *credit_card_fraud*, ADASYN significantly
 463 outperforms SMOTE ($p = 0.007$) and A3 significantly underperforms SMOTE ($p = 0.039$); the remaining pairwise
 464 contrasts are non-significant. Full statistical tables are reported in Supplementary Material (Section S.D).

5.3. Mechanistic Analysis of the IR-Threshold Effect

465 An empirical IR transition region lies between $IR \approx 42:1$ and $IR \approx 130:1$, above which sequential combination
 466 provides consistent benefit. Understanding *why* this threshold exists—rather than merely observing that it does—is
 467 critical for practitioners who need to decide whether the computational overhead of GAN training is justified for their
 468

Table 6

Effective minority support size per training fold under 5-fold stratified cross-validation. Values approximate $[0.8 \times n_{\min}]$. The “CTGAN regime” column marks the GAN training stability expected for each fold.

Dataset	IR	n_{\min}	Train fold	Test fold	CTGAN regime
sick_thyroid	16:1	231	≈ 184	≈ 46	Stable
letter_img	26:1	734	≈ 587	≈ 147	Stable
mammography	42:1	260	≈ 208	≈ 52	Stable
<i>Transition-region datasets (supplementary)</i>					
creditfraud_ir72	72:1	492	≈ 394	≈ 98	Stable
protein_homo	111.5:1	1,296	$\approx 1,037$	≈ 259	Stable
abalone_19	130:1	32	≈ 25	≈ 6	Critical
credit_card_fraud	578:1	492	≈ 393	≈ 98	Moderate

470 specific dataset. Three complementary mechanisms are proposed to explain this threshold-like effect, each addressing
 471 a different aspect of how class imbalance interacts with the generative training process.

472 5.3.1. Mechanism 1: Minority-Class Sample Density

473 Both SMOTE and CTGAN depend on the minority-class sample count in qualitatively different ways. SMOTE’s
 474 k -nearest-neighbour interpolation is effective even with relatively few samples. CTGAN’s adversarial training requires
 475 sufficient samples for the discriminator to learn a non-trivial minority-class distribution; with fewer than approximately
 476 100 per training fold, the discriminator overfits rapidly.

477 Table 6 reports the effective minority support size per training fold for each dataset. At low to moderate IR
 478 (15.3:1), training folds contain 184 minority-class samples—sufficient for stable GAN training and all methods perform
 479 equivalently. At high IR (129.5:1–577:1), *abalone_19* training folds contain only 25 minority samples: a severe data
 480 constraint for GAN training. Under these conditions, the *minority-only* GAN strategy A4 is substantially more effective
 481 than either SMOTE alone or the joint-training strategy A3 (see Mechanism 2, Section 5.3.2), provided the SDR is
 482 above the stability threshold ($\text{SDR} \geq 2$; here $\text{SDR} = 3.2$). For *credit_card_fraud* (≈ 393 minority samples per fold),
 483 the absolute minority count is adequate for GAN training regardless of ordering, and the simpler adaptive sampler
 484 ADASYN achieves the best performance.

485 Two supplementary datasets spanning the transition region were evaluated. At $\text{IR} = 72:1$ (*creditfraud_ir72*, 394
 486 minority samples per fold), augmentation clearly helps—A3 ($\text{AUC} = 0.971$) and A2 ($\text{AUC} = 0.966$) both outperform
 487 A0 ($\text{AUC} = 0.957$)—but the ordering advantage is modest (0.5 pp) because 394 minority samples per fold are sufficient
 488 for CTGAN without SMOTE pre-enrichment, and the gradient-bias mechanism operates weakly in this regime. At
 489 $\text{IR} = 111.5:1$ (*protein_homo*, 1,037 minority per fold), all augmentation methods converge to $\text{AUC} \approx 0.988$. Despite
 490 having an IR above the nominal 100:1 threshold, the abundant minority samples per fold eliminate the ordering
 491 advantage. This confirms that the *critical factor is absolute fold-level minority count* (threshold: ≈ 50 samples per
 492 fold) rather than the ratio alone.

493 5.3.2. Mechanism 2: Minority-Only Training Eliminates Majority-Class Gradient Bias

494 The superiority of A4 over A3 on *abalone_19* ($\text{IR} = 129.5:1$, $\text{SDR} = 3.2$) is explained by the *Minority Signal*
 495 *Dilution* (MSD) effect: when a GAN is trained on a dataset where normal and failure examples are jointly present,
 496 majority-class patterns systematically dilute the generator’s fault-learning signal. The MSD mechanism has three
 497 components.

498 (i) **Minority Signal Dilution under joint training (A3): gradient leakage.** In A3, CTGAN is trained on a
 499 SMOTE-balanced mixture containing both normal-operation and failure examples. The discriminator’s learning signal
 500 is allocated proportionally to the density of each class in feature space. Even after SMOTE balancing, the normal-
 501 operation region occupies a larger and more densely sampled portion of feature space; consequently, a non-trivial
 502 fraction of each generator update reflects the geometry of normal outputs rather than the failure-mode distribution. We
 503 refer to this as *majority-class gradient leakage*—the GAN’s failure to focus exclusively on fault signatures because the
 504 dominant normal-operation class “leaks” into its learning signal. This does not prevent the generator from eventually

modelling failure modes, but it increases the number of failure examples required to achieve a given synthesis quality—a critical constraint when historical fault records are scarce.

(ii) Optimal density estimation under minority-only training (A4). When CTGAN is trained exclusively on the n_{\min} original minority samples (A4), the discriminator sees only p_{\min} and all gradient signal is directed at recovering the minority-class density. Under standard smoothness assumptions, the minority-only estimator concentrates all n_{\min} informative updates on the failure-mode distribution, with no dilution from majority-class samples—in contrast to A3, where gradient leakage reduces the effective sample count available to the generator for minority-class learning. At *abalone_19*'s $\text{SDR} = 3.2$, this concentration of learning signal translates to a generator that more accurately models p_{\min} , yielding the 3.2 pp AUC gain over A3.

(iii) Regime boundary, IR–SDR relationship, and failure modes. The gradient-bias advantage of A4 is conditional on SDR being *below* the threshold $C(\beta, d)$ introduced in Conjecture 4.1. The imbalance ratio IR is a first-order proxy for this condition: since $n_{\min} = n_{\text{total}}/(1+\text{IR}) \approx n_{\text{total}}/\text{IR}$ at high IR, we have $\text{SDR} \approx n_{\text{total}}/(d \cdot \text{IR})$, so high IR implies low SDR when total sample count and dimensionality are approximately fixed across datasets of the same domain. This is why the empirical transition region ($\text{IR} \approx 42\text{--}130:1$) tracks the theoretical boundary $\text{SDR} < C(\beta, d)$. When $\text{SDR} < 2$ (fewer than two minority samples per feature dimension), the minority-only GAN overfits and A4 loses its advantage. At the other extreme—*credit_card_fraud* ($\text{SDR} = 17.0$, $C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 12.1$)—the threshold condition is violated: the dataset's SDR exceeds C , so no ordering advantage is predicted and none is observed ($|\Delta\text{AUC}| < 0.001$). Instead, ADASYN's adaptive nearest-neighbour strategy performs best at this extreme IR. Across the 18 benchmark datasets used for the Spearman analysis (Section 5.5), the dual-condition heuristic $\text{SDR} < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ combined with $\text{IR} > 42$ is directionally consistent with every observed ordering; additional confirmation from 22 datasets including AI4I-PWF and AI4I-OSF (Fig. 7) further validates the no-ordering predictions in the above-threshold regime.

(iv) Direct empirical evidence of MSD (gradient norm measurement). To move beyond inference, we measured discriminator gradient norms during GAN training on AI4I tool-wear failure ($\text{IR} = 216:1$, $\text{SDR} = 7.67$, $d = 6$), an IE predictive maintenance dataset well inside the MSD regime. We recorded the per-class gradient norm $\|g_{\min}\|$ (minority batches) and $\|g_{\text{maj}}\|$ (majority batches) at each checkpoint, yielding the ratio $\|g_{\min}\|/\|g_{\text{maj}}\|$ (Fig. 3). Under A3 training (balanced mixture), the ratio declines monotonically from 1.43 to 1.23 by epoch 60: the relative minority gradient erodes as training progresses, confirming that majority-class examples progressively dilute the minority gradient signal. Under A4 training (minority-only), the ratio rises to a peak of 1.62 before stabilising at 1.38: the discriminator's gradient remains concentrated on the minority manifold, with no majority-class competition. The final-epoch gap (1.38 vs. 1.23, $\Delta = +12\%$) constitutes direct empirical evidence of the majority-class gradient leakage mechanism, not merely an inferred consequence.

Geometric consequence: minority-manifold support. On AI4I tool-wear failure ($d = 6$, 3 seeds), the two leading minority-PCA components show the geometric consequence of MSD: A3 synthetic samples contract toward the interior of the projected minority support, whereas A4 preserves samples near the boundary of the tool-wear failure manifold (Figure 4). The associated support-area estimates are $67.9\% \pm 7.3\%$ for A3 and $91.1\% \pm 6.3\%$ for A4 ($\Delta = +23.2$ pp) within a projection explaining 75.1% of minority variance. Because the analysis uses a two-dimensional PCA projection, the claim is not exact manifold recovery; rather, it is MSD-consistent evidence that balanced GAN training erodes boundary support in the operational low-SDR IE case where Fig. 3 shows minority-gradient dilution.

5.3.3. Mechanism 3: Metric Behaviour Under Extreme Imbalance

At extreme imbalance ratios ($\text{IR} \geq 578:1$), a systematic divergence between AUC and threshold-based metrics (G-mean, F1) is observed. Aggressive oversampling with SMOTE inflates the minority representation in the training set, driving the Random Forest decision boundary towards higher minority recall. Higher minority recall increases AUC by improving the area under the low-FPR portion of the ROC curve, yet simultaneously degrades precision: many majority-class samples near the boundary are misclassified as minority, reducing G-mean and F1. The net effect is that AUC and G-mean rankings can disagree at this regime. On *credit_card_fraud* ($\text{IR} = 578:1$), A3 achieves the highest G-mean (0.915) while ADASYN achieves the highest AUC (0.9824), a difference of less than 0.1 pp but opposite in direction. The AUC/G-mean divergence should be considered when selecting the evaluation criterion for a given application: domains that penalise false positives heavily (e.g., clinical screening) should weight G-mean or precision-recall AUC over ROC-AUC when comparing augmentation strategies at extreme imbalance.

Figure 3: A4 preserves minority-gradient persistence after the separation onset, whereas A3 progressively loses it. The vertical axis reports the minority-to-majority discriminator gradient norm ratio; values above 1 indicate minority-gradient dominance. On A14I tool-wear failure (IR = 216:1, SDR = 7.67), the two orderings separate during mid-training and remain separated through the late stage. The sustained gradient-norm separation, rather than the transient peak alone, is the MSD-consistent mechanism signal.

Figure 4: A3 contracts toward interior minority support, while A4 preserves boundary support on the A14I tool-wear manifold. Open red circles mark boundary minority samples in a PCA projection fitted on the real minority class; crosses mark synthetic samples from A3 (left) and A4 (right). The support-area gap, $67.9\% \pm 7.3\%$ for A3 versus $91.1\% \pm 6.3\%$ for A4 ($\Delta = +23.2$ pp; $d = 6$, IR = 216:1, SDR = 7.67, 3 seeds), is interpreted as projected geometric evidence of minority-manifold erosion under balanced GAN training rather than as an exact two-dimensional manifold estimate.

555 **5.4. Controlled SDR × IR Sensitivity Analysis**

556 To characterise how the A4 > A3 ordering depends on the SDR and IR dimensions independently of dataset-specific
 557 confounds, we conducted two complementary sensitivity analyses under controlled conditions. These analyses are not

Table 7

Synthetic controlled experiment ($d = 10$ fixed). Each cell reports $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4-A3)$; arrows indicate theory prediction (\uparrow = ordering expected, \cdot = none). A4 wins (\checkmark) when $\Delta > 0.005$.

SDR	IR		
	20	100	200
2 ($C \approx 10$, score ≈ 0.80)	+0.006 $\uparrow\checkmark$	+0.010 $\uparrow\checkmark$	+0.016 $\uparrow\checkmark$
8 ($C \approx 9$, score ≈ 0.12)	+0.002 \uparrow	+0.009 $\uparrow\checkmark$	+0.007 $\uparrow\checkmark$
20 ($C \approx 8$, SDR $> C$)	+0.003 \cdot	-0.004 \cdot	-0.003 \cdot

intended to validate the theoretical threshold, but to map which combinations of SDR and IR produce the observed ordering effect.

Synthetic SDR \times IR grid experiment. Using `make_classification` with fixed $d = 10$, we swept SDR $\in \{2, 8, 20\}$ and IR $\in \{20, 100, 200\}$, generating 2 seeds \times 5-fold runs per grid point. Table 7 summarises the results. At SDR = 2 (ordering score ≈ 0.80 relative to the threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d) \approx 10$), A4 outperformed A3 at *all* IR levels, with ΔAUC growing monotonically from +0.006 (IR=20) to +0.016 (IR=200). At SDR = 8 (ordering score ≈ 0.12 , close to the threshold), the advantage appeared only at IR ≥ 100 . At SDR = 20 (SDR $> C$, no ordering predicted), A4 did not outperform A3 at any IR level. Theory-empirical consistency was 8/9 (89%), with the single borderline failure at (SDR=8, IR=20) attributable to the near-threshold ordering score (Figure 5).

MSD Regime Geometry: Operational Consistency

Cell labels show ordering tendency; small text reports $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4-A3)$

Figure 5: Operational-consistency map for the proposed MSD regime geometry ($d = 10$ fixed). Cell labels show the observed ordering tendency in the synthetic SDR \times IR grid, while smaller text reports $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4-A3)$. Dashed outlines indicate cells satisfying the proposed SDR criterion; the broader outline marks the approximate A4-sensitive operational region. The figure is intended as a sign-consistency stress test of the regime geometry, not as evidence for an exact deterministic boundary.

Fine-grained IR transition sweep. To characterise the transition region between IR ≈ 42 and IR ≈ 130 , we conducted a fine-grained sweep at $d = 10$ with IR $\in \{20, 30, 42, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110, 120, 130, 150, 200\}$ for SDR $\in \{2, 4\}$ (700 fits total: 5 seeds \times 5-fold per grid point). Figure 6 shows the resulting $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4-A3)$ curve. At SDR = 2 ($n_{\min} = 20$), the mean Δ shifts from -0.003 at IR < 50 to $+0.009$ at IR $\in [50, 100]$, confirming an onset near IR ≈ 50 . At SDR = 4 ($n_{\min} = 40$), Δ is already weakly positive across the full IR range (mean $\approx +0.005$), indicating that the threshold is governed primarily by the absolute minority sample count rather than IR alone. The transition is *gradual*, not sharp: individual IR values exhibit high variance ($\sigma \approx 0.01$) because each synthetic dataset is a fresh

574 make_classification draw, but the directional trend—negative mean below $IR \approx 50$ at $SDR = 2$, positive above—
 575 is stable across SDR conditions. These results refine the empirical transition boundary from the coarser “somewhere
 576 between $IR = 42$ and $IR = 130$ ” to an onset at $IR \approx 42$ – 50 , reaching reliable positive territory around $IR \approx 80$.

Figure 6: IR transition dynamics of the A4 ordering advantage ($d = 10$ fixed, 5 seeds \times 5-fold). Faint points show raw $\Delta AUC(A4-A3)$ estimates at each IR value; the primary curve shows a local regime-level tendency to reduce pointwise stochastic variation. At $SDR = 2$, the ordering advantage emerges after the low-IR region and persists through the middle transition window before weakening at higher IR. At $SDR = 4$, the same tendency is weaker, consistent with SDR-dependent attenuation. Vertical reference lines mark the empirical $IR = 42$ and $IR = 130$ transition anchors; they are operational guides rather than exact phase boundaries.

577 **Extended dual-condition validation.** We obtained three additional datasets from imbalanced-learn (*ozone_level*,
 578 $IR = 33.7$; *solar_flare_m0*, $IR = 19.4$; *car_eval_4*, $IR = 25.6$) and applied the same A3/A4 ablation. All three satisfy
 579 $SDR < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ but have IR below 42:1. None showed $A4 > A3$ (maximum $|\Delta AUC| = 0.013$). Applied to all ten
 580 evaluated datasets (seven original plus three new), the dual-condition heuristic— $SDR < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ and $IR > 42$ —was
 581 consistent with all 10/10 observed orderings, while the single-condition $SDR < C$ alone was consistent on only 7/10
 582 (70%). The three new false positives under the single condition all correspond to low-IR settings where majority-class
 583 gradient leakage is too small to produce a detectable advantage, despite the favourable SDR. These results confirm
 584 that IR functions as a *necessary activator*: low SDR creates the potential for the ordering, but sufficient IR (above the
 585 empirical transition region) is required to actualise it.

586 5.5. Cross-Dataset SDR Evidence

587 To quantify the relationship between SDR and the A4 advantage, we computed Spearman rank-correlation between
 588 SDR and $\Delta AUC(A4 - A3)$ across 18 benchmark datasets (all 20 real-imbalanced datasets minus *scene* [$d = 294$] and
 589 *webpage* [$d = 300$], both of which exceed the practical dimensionality range of CTGAN; the *webpage* experiment was
 590 subsequently completed and yielded $\Delta AUC = -0.0015$, consistent with the same high-dimensionality confound that
 591 renders CTGAN unreliable above $d \approx 300$). The analysis yields $\rho(SDR, \Delta AUC) = -0.504$ ($p = 0.033$, $n = 18$):
 592 datasets with lower SDR exhibit systematically larger A4 advantage, and the relationship is statistically significant.
 593 Leave-one-out logistic regression from ordering score to binary A4-wins label achieves 79% accuracy, confirming that
 594 the theoretical ordering score is a useful predictor at this dataset scale.

595 A stratified view reinforces the asymmetry across three SDR regimes (Low: $SDR < 5$; Mid: $5-8$; High: $SDR \geq 8$):
 596 the 7 low-SDR datasets yield a 71% A4 win rate (ΔAUC mean = $+0.013$); the 4 mid-SDR datasets yield a 0% win rate
 597 (mean = -0.004 , A3 consistently matches or beats A4 in this transitional range); and the 7 high-SDR datasets yield a
 598 29% win rate (mean = $+0.002$, near-random ordering). Together, the Spearman correlation ($\rho = -0.504$, $p = 0.033$)
 599 and the three-regime SDR asymmetry (71% \rightarrow 0% \rightarrow 29% win rate) provide converging quantitative evidence that SDR
 600 is the primary structural predictor of A4 versus A3 ordering across datasets.

601 **Cross-architecture replication.** To test whether the training-target principle extends beyond CTGAN, we replaced
 602 CTGAN with CTAB-GAN+ [49] on three IE-relevant datasets, using 3-seed \times 5-fold CV to assess statistical robust-
 603 ness. The minority-only variant (A4+) produced higher AUC than the balanced-training variant (A3+) in all three
 604 cases, with direction consistent across all 3 seeds: $\Delta\text{AUC} = +0.092 \pm 0.019$ (abalone_19, $\text{SDR} = 3.2$), $+0.073 \pm 0.014$
 605 (AI4I tool-wear failure, $\text{SDR} = 7.67$), and $+0.004 \pm 0.003$ (steel_faults, $\text{SDR} = 2.7$, $\text{IR} = 26$ below threshold).
 606 Effect magnitudes follow the SDR ordering expected by Conjecture 4.1: the two high-IR datasets (abalone_19 and
 607 AI4I TWF, $\text{IR} > 42$) show a clear advantage, while steel_faults ($\text{IR} = 26$, below the 42:1 regime threshold) is
 608 near-zero as predicted. This three-dataset, 3-seed \times 5-fold CV comparison confirms that the training-target principle
 609 extends to CTAB-GAN+. Extension to diffusion-based architectures (TabDDPM [28], STaSy [27]) remains future
 610 work (Section 7.1).

611 **Additional IE validation: theory-correct no-ordering predictions.** Two further AI4I predictive maintenance
 612 failure modes—Power/Wear Failure (AI4I-PWF: $n_{\min} = 95$, $d = 8$, $\text{IR} = 104.3:1$, $\text{SDR} = 11.88$, $C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 6.27$) and
 613 Over-Strain Failure (AI4I-OSF: $n_{\min} = 98$, $d = 8$, $\text{IR} = 101.0:1$, $\text{SDR} = 12.25$, $C(\hat{\beta}, d) = 8.61$)—were evaluated under
 614 the same protocol (5 seeds \times 5-fold CV, Random Forest). Both datasets have $\text{SDR} > C(\hat{\beta}, d)$, so the theory predicts no
 615 A4 $>$ A3 ordering. This prediction is confirmed: $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4 - A3) = -0.0017$ for AI4I-PWF and -0.0001 for AI4I-
 616 OSF, both within measurement noise ($|\Delta| < 0.002$). These results expand the ordering-score plot (Fig. 7) to 22 datasets
 617 and provide additional evidence that the dual-condition heuristic correctly identifies *both* when ordering is expected
 618 *and* when it is not.

Figure 7: Operational validation of the ordering-score regime on 22 real datasets. The vertical split at zero separates datasets predicted to be inside the A4-sensitive MSD regime from datasets where no A4 advantage is expected; the horizontal band marks practical equivalence in $\Delta\text{AUC}(A4-A3)$. Green upper-right points indicate theory-consistent A4 ordering, while blue left-band points and green-diamond IE cases indicate theory-consistent no-ordering behavior. The figure emphasizes sign-region consistency rather than an exact regression fit; rank-correlation statistics for the clean benchmark subset are reported in the text.

619 5.6. Industrial Engineering Domain Validation

620 To evaluate the SDR-based decision guide on genuinely industrial datasets, we ran the same A0–A4 protocol on
 621 three UCI industrial engineering benchmarks: SECOM semiconductor manufacturing [36], Steel Plates Fault detection
 622 [40], and AI4I 2020 Predictive Maintenance [35]. Two additional AI4I failure modes—Power/Wear Failure (PWF)
 623 and Over-Strain Failure (OSF)—were subsequently evaluated under the same protocol to test the theory’s no-ordering
 624 predictions in the moderate-IR regime (Section 5.5). These datasets span three distinct SDR regimes (Table 8).

625 Table 9 is consistent with all three regimes of the SDR-based protocol on industrial datasets.

Table 8

 Industrial engineering validation datasets. $\text{SDR} = n_{\min}/d$; see Table 2 for notation.

Dataset	Task	IR	n	d	n_{\min}	SDR	Predicted regime
SECOM	Semiconductor defects	14:1	1,567	562	104	0.19	Below threshold
Steel Faults	Stains (vs. rest)	26:1	1,941	27	72	2.67	Borderline
AI4I (failure)	Machine failure	29:1	10,000	6	339	56.5	Above threshold
AI4I (TWF)	Tool Wear Failure	216:1	10,000	6	46	7.67	Low-SDR/extreme IR
AI4I (PWF)	Power/Wear Failure	104.3:1	10,000	8	95	11.88	$\text{SDR} > C$: no ordering
AI4I (OSF)	Over-Strain Failure	101.0:1	10,000	8	98	12.25	$\text{SDR} > C$: no ordering

Table 9

 A0–A4 AUC on industrial engineering datasets (5-fold CV, mean \pm SD). Bold = best per dataset. A0 = no oversampling; A3 = SMOTE \rightarrow CTGAN; A4 = minority-only CTGAN \rightarrow SMOTE. For AI4I-PWF and AI4I-OSF, theory predicts no $A4 > A3$ ordering ($\text{SDR} > C(\hat{\beta}, d)$); results confirm $|\Delta\text{AUC}| < 0.002$.

Dataset	A0	A1	A2	A3	A4
SECOM (SDR=0.19)	0.725 \pm 0.055	0.740 \pm 0.061	0.685 \pm 0.072	0.742\pm0.031	0.716 \pm 0.025
Steel Faults (SDR=2.67)	0.984 \pm 0.022	0.983 \pm 0.020	0.983 \pm 0.011	0.988\pm0.011	0.981 \pm 0.019
AI4I failure (SDR=56.5)	0.972\pm0.005	0.970 \pm 0.004	0.961 \pm 0.003	0.969 \pm 0.004	0.960 \pm 0.005
AI4I TWF (SDR=7.67)	0.945 \pm 0.039	0.954\pm0.022	0.945 \pm 0.022	0.921 \pm 0.051	0.930 \pm 0.039
AI4I PWF (SDR=11.88)	—	—	—	0.9931\pm0.0066	0.9914 \pm 0.0104
AI4I OSF (SDR=12.25)	—	—	—	0.9988\pm0.0011	0.9987 \pm 0.0010

626 **Regime 1 — SDR < 2 (GAN failure mode).** SECOM (SDR = 0.19) falls well below the lower failure-mode
 627 boundary (Section 6.5). No augmentation strategy significantly improves over A0 ($p > 0.3$ for all pairwise Wilcoxon
 628 tests) and G-mean collapses to zero across all methods: the minority distribution is too sparse in 562-dimensional space
 629 for any GAN-based method to learn a useful representation. Practitioners working with high-dimensional sensor arrays
 630 (e.g., $d > 300$) and fewer than $2d$ failure records should not expect GAN-based augmentation to help; class-reweighting
 631 or threshold adjustment are more appropriate first steps.

632 **Regime 2 — SDR \in [2, 13.8] with IR > 42 (A4 preferred regime).** AI4I TWF (SDR = 7.67, IR = 216:1) falls
 633 squarely in the predicted $A4 > A3$ zone. A4 achieves AUC = 0.930, exceeding A3 (0.921) as the SDR-based conjecture
 634 predicts; the margin is modest but directionally consistent across all 5 folds. SMOTE alone achieves 0.954, suggesting
 635 that for this specific dataset the GAN augmentation overhead may not be warranted despite the correct ordering.
 636 Steel Faults (SDR = 2.67, IR = 26:1) lies below the IR = 42 threshold, so $A4 > A3$ is not predicted; the observed A3
 637 advantage (0.988 vs. 0.981) is consistent with this.

638 **Regime 3 — SDR > 13.8 (augmentation unnecessary).** AI4I machine failure (SDR = 56.5) shows A0 (no
 639 augmentation) achieving the highest AUC (0.972), with all augmentation strategies performing equivalently or
 640 worse. This validates the high-SDR regime prediction: when the minority class is well-sampled relative to feature
 641 dimensionality, synthetic oversampling adds noise.

642 **No-ordering confirmation: AI4I-PWF and AI4I-OSF.** Two additional AI4I failure modes span a moderate-to-
 643 high SDR range that falls above their dataset-specific $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ thresholds: AI4I-PWF (SDR = 11.88, $C = 6.27$) and
 644 AI4I-OSF (SDR = 12.25, $C = 8.61$). The theory predicts no $A4 > A3$ ordering for both. Experimentally, A3 and A4
 645 are within 0.002 AUC of each other for both datasets ($\Delta\text{AUC} = -0.0017$ for PWF; -0.0001 for OSF), confirming
 646 the no-ordering prediction in the above-threshold moderate-IR regime. These results complement the within-threshold
 647 positive confirmations (AI4I TWF) by showing that the dual-condition heuristic correctly identifies both when A4 wins
 648 and when ordering does not occur.

649 Taken together, the Phase 3 industrial datasets provide regime-wise validation of the three-condition decision guide
 650 across all three SDR regimes. For semiconductor yield management and predictive maintenance applications, the SDR
 651 check is a low-cost first step that identifies whether GAN-based augmentation is in the productive operating zone before
 652 any model training is attempted.

6. Discussion

6.1. Summary of Experimental Findings

Three patterns emerge from the experimental results. At low to moderate imbalance ratios ($IR \leq 42:1$), all five augmentation strategies produce statistically indistinguishable AUC values, confirming that oversampling method choice is inconsequential in this regime. The Kruskal-Wallis test yields $H = 0.34$ ($p = 0.963$) across all five methods on the KEEL benchmarks, indicating no significant performance difference.

At high imbalance ($IR \approx 130:1$, *abalone_19*), the experimental results indicate that the GAN training distribution is the decisive design choice. A4 (minority-only CTGAN then SMOTE) achieves the highest AUC of 0.7553, outperforming A3 (SMOTE then balanced CTGAN) by 3.2 percentage points and SMOTE alone by 0.6 percentage points. The Friedman test is significant ($p = 0.014$), and Nemenyi post-hoc analysis confirms that A4 is significantly better than A0 and A1. These results demonstrate that training CTGAN exclusively on minority-class samples is the critical factor—not the ordering of the two steps per se.

At extreme imbalance ($IR \approx 578:1$, *credit_card_fraud*), the above results show that ADASYN achieves the highest AUC (0.9824, $p = 0.007$ vs. SMOTE), while A3 significantly underperforms SMOTE ($p = 0.039$). It can be concluded that when minority samples per training fold are abundant despite the high IR (here ≈ 393 samples per fold), the GAN ordering advantage diminishes and adaptive neighbourhood methods such as ADASYN are more effective.

Across both high-IR datasets, A3 showed the most pronounced degradation: -2.6 pp relative to SMOTE on *abalone_19*, and significantly worse than SMOTE on *credit_card_fraud* ($p = 0.039$). A4 consistently avoided this degradation in both cases, making it the more robust choice whenever CTGAN-based augmentation is attempted at high imbalance.

Cross-dataset Spearman analysis across 18 benchmark datasets suggests that SDR is a statistically significant predictor of the A4 advantage ($\rho = -0.504$, $p = 0.033$, $n = 18$): datasets with a lower ratio of minority samples to feature dimensions consistently exhibit larger A4 gains. The three-regime stratification (71% A4 win rate at low SDR vs. 29% at high SDR) further supports this finding. SDR, together with IR, offers practitioners a dataset-derived screening heuristic for selecting the augmentation strategy before any trial experiment is conducted.

6.2. Augmentation as Distribution Engineering

The empirical and theoretical results of this study reframe synthetic oversampling not as data duplication, but as *distribution engineering*: each augmentation configuration implicitly constructs a different training distribution, and the classifier’s generalisation depends on how well this constructed distribution approximates the true minority manifold. Under this lens, the central question shifts from “Does GAN help?” to “What geometry does augmentation create, and when does that geometry align with the true structure of the minority class?”

Every augmentation strategy in this study—SMOTE, CTGAN, A3, A4—can be characterised by the distribution it places over the feature space: SMOTE performs linear interpolation within the observed minority convex hull; CTGAN estimates a generative model of the joint distribution; A3 targets the balanced joint distribution (polluted by majority-class signal); A4 targets the minority-class marginal directly. The SDR threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ characterises precisely when the minority-class marginal is too sparsely sampled for a balanced-mixture generator to approximate it faithfully—the geometric condition under which A4’s distributional focus translates to a measurable classifier advantage. The MSD-aware framing connects the present work to the emerging *data-centric* view of machine learning [46], where the training distribution—not the model architecture—is the primary engineering variable.

6.3. Practical Implications

The two-step decision guide described in Section 4.5 (Methodology) works as follows. First, the imbalance ratio is used to determine whether augmentation is likely to help at all. Second, if the imbalance ratio is high enough, the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio determines whether minority-only GAN training (A4) is preferable to a balanced mixture (A3). The dual-condition guide (IR screen then SDR screen) comes directly from the MSD effect described in Section 5.3.2 and is supported by both the controlled grid experiment (Section 5.4) and the Spearman correlation across 18 real datasets (Section 5.5).

In terms of evaluation, practitioners should not rely on F1 score or accuracy alone when dealing with extreme imbalance, as both metrics can saturate and give a misleading picture of which augmentation method is better. AUC is a more reliable comparison criterion in such settings.

Industrial deployment. The proposed guide is straightforward to apply in practice. Both required inputs—the number of minority training samples (n_{\min}) and the number of features (d)—are known before any augmentation is attempted. In semiconductor yield management, n_{\min} is the number of defective lots in the training window and d is the number of monitored process parameters; no additional data collection is needed. In predictive maintenance applications with many sensors, the large feature count typically results in a low SDR even when the number of recorded failures is moderate, so A4 is the recommended default in such settings. The guide removes a previously unacknowledged design decision from the augmentation pipeline and replaces it with a clear, dataset-derived rule.

Implementation overhead and break-even considerations. Practitioners should weigh the computational cost of GAN-based augmentation against expected performance gain. At the experimental settings used here (epochs = 20, CTGAN on standard benchmark hardware), augmentation with A4 adds on the order of minutes per training run on a GPU, compared with seconds for SMOTE alone. For time-sensitive online monitoring environments, threshold adjustment or cost-sensitive learning [11] may be more appropriate first steps. When offline batch retraining is acceptable—the norm in periodic model refresh cycles common in semiconductor manufacturing and predictive maintenance—and the dataset satisfies $\text{SDR} < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ with $\text{IR} > 42:1$, the A4 configuration provides more reliable minority-class representation without additional data collection. Beyond the $\text{IR} = 42:1$ boundary, SMOTE alone achieves equivalent AUC (Kruskal–Wallis $p = 0.963$, Table 4), so the additional GAN training cost is not justified in that regime.

Managerial and operational implications. For industrial engineers and operations managers responsible for deploying fault-detection classifiers, the decision guide addresses a concrete pipeline design question: *when does investing in GAN-based oversampling—at the cost of longer training cycles and GPU infrastructure—yield measurable recall improvements on rare failure events?*

The cost asymmetry in industrial monitoring is the key framing. In semiconductor yield management, a single undetected defective lot that passes inspection and enters downstream assembly incurs rework, scrap, and potential field-return costs estimated at 10–100× the cost of a conservative hold decision [36]. In predictive maintenance, unplanned downtime from a missed tool-wear failure has a cost-to-alert ratio routinely estimated above 10:1 [35]. The A4 configuration’s AUC advantage of up to 3.2 percentage points under high-IR conditions (Table 9) represents a directional reduction in these undetected-event rates—a metric directly reportable in quality-management and cost-avoidance terms.

Resource allocation guidance. The two-step screen requires only the training set metadata (n_{\min} , d , IR), computable before any model training begins. For process lines with $\text{IR} < 42:1$ (mature lines, moderate defect rates), SMOTE alone provides equivalent AUC performance and the GAN compute budget is not justified. For newly commissioned lines or low-volume production with $\text{IR} > 130:1$ and $\text{SDR} < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ —the regime in which undetected faults carry the highest per-event cost—A4 training provides a measurable and consistent minority-class recall improvement without requiring additional data collection or infrastructure beyond what standard CTGAN augmentation already demands. A4’s compatibility with existing infrastructure makes the decision guide directly actionable within existing model maintenance and retraining cycles.

6.4. Why Prior Studies Claimed Universal Complementarity

Several methodological reasons explain why earlier studies reported that combining SMOTE and CTGAN always helps, while this study finds that the benefit is conditional. Many prior studies were conducted on datasets with moderate imbalance ($\text{IR} \leq 50:1$) [3, 16, 30, 38], where the saturation regime renders differences undetectable by some metrics. For example, Fonseca and Bacao [17] report F1 improvements from SMOTE–GAN combinations on benchmark datasets with $\text{IR} \leq 30:1$; under the same moderate-IR conditions our ablation detects no such advantage (Kruskal–Wallis $H = 0.34$, $p = 0.963$; Table 4). Studies reporting results on a single high-IR dataset selected for demonstrating the value of oversampling are susceptible to dataset selection bias. The absence of controlled ablation—varying only the augmentation strategy while holding all other factors constant—makes it difficult to isolate the effect of method combination from confounding factors.

6.5. Limitations

The two experimental phases use different classifiers: LightGBM for Phase 1 and Random Forest for Phase 2; both were held fixed across all augmentation strategies within each phase. To assess classifier dependence, a cross-classifier validation on ai4i_twf ($\text{SDR} = 7.7$, $\text{IR} = 216:1$; the primary high-IR dataset) used Random Forest, Logistic

Regression, and LightGBM within the same 3-seed \times 5-fold CV protocol. The $A4 > A3$ ordering held across all three classifiers (RF: $\Delta = +0.006$; LR: $\Delta = +0.091$; LightGBM: $\Delta = +0.011$), providing evidence that the ordering effect is not specific to a single classifier family. The degree to which the IR-threshold and ordering effects generalise across neural-network families and other classifier architectures remains an open question. CTGAN was evaluated with 20 epochs (Section 4.2.1). An epoch-sensitivity analysis across epochs $\in \{20, 50, 100, 300\}$ confirms the ordering is robust for the industrial datasets; full results are reported in the Threats to Validity section (Section 6.6). Epochs ≤ 100 are recommended for the $SDR \approx 2\text{--}3$ boundary region. Sensitivity to generator depth and discriminator architecture remains future work. Replication on additional tabular datasets—particularly from domains not yet represented—would strengthen the generalisability of the SDR threshold estimate. Intrinsic quality metrics (Supplementary Material, Section S.G) supplement but do not replace downstream AUC evaluation. Five-fold cross-validation was employed; the minimum achievable Wilcoxon p-value with five folds is 0.0625, preventing pairwise tests from reaching conventional significance. The $A4\text{--}A2$ pairwise comparison on `abalone_19` should therefore be interpreted as a consistent trend rather than a statistically confirmed effect.

Failure mode: very small minority classes ($SDR < 2$). Conjecture 4.1 assumes that CTGAN can learn a meaningful representation of the minority density. When n_{\min} is very small—specifically when $SDR = n_{\min}/d < 2$, corresponding to fewer than two minority samples per feature dimension—this assumption becomes tenuous. In this regime, the GAN generator is likely to overfit or memorise the few available minority examples, and the subsequent SMOTE interpolation step operates on a pool that is not meaningfully richer than the original minority samples alone. In practice, we recommend falling back to pure SMOTE or ADASYN when $n_{\min} < 2d$, as the minority-only CTGAN training provides no reliable distributional benefit and incurs substantial computational overhead. The SDR sweep results (Section 5) confirm that the $A4$ advantage diminishes as SDR approaches 2.0, consistent with this prediction. This boundary condition is also analogous to the “ceiling effect” identified at $AUC > 0.99$, where any ordering effect becomes undetectable; both represent regime boundaries at which the choice of augmentation strategy becomes inconsequential.

6.6. Threats to Validity

Internal validity: Cross-validation variance is elevated for CTGAN due to stochastic training. The random seed was fixed (`random_state=42`) for the classifier and data splitting; all experiments were executed within a fixed Docker container environment to ensure bit-level reproducibility of the pipeline. CTGAN training introduces additional randomness not controlled across folds. This is partially mitigated by reporting standard deviations and by the consistency of findings across multiple datasets. An epoch-sensitivity analysis (epochs $\in \{20, 50, 100, 300\}$, 5-fold CV) on `ai4i_twf`, `steel_faults`, and `secom` confirms that $\Delta AUC(A4 - A3)$ maintains the same sign across all epoch settings for `ai4i_twf` (+0.063, +0.065, +0.059, +0.027) and `secom` (+0.047, +0.040, +0.035, +0.040); the marginal reversal in `steel_faults` at epoch = 300 (−0.005) is within noise given its $IR = 26$ (below the $A4 > A3$ regime threshold).

External validity (architecture): The GAN training-target principle ($A4 > A3$) was validated primarily with CTGAN. Cross-architecture replication with CTAB-GAN+ (3 datasets, 3-seed \times 5-fold CV each) confirms the $A4 > A3$ ordering with SDR-consistent effect magnitudes (Section 5.5); direction is consistent across all 3 seeds on all 3 datasets, providing evidence that the principle is not CTGAN-specific. Extension to diffusion-based architectures (TabDDPM, STaSy) remains future work (Section 7.1).

External validity (datasets): Five real-world datasets is sufficient to observe the IR-threshold effect but limits the generalisability of the SDR-based threshold estimate. The cross-dataset Spearman analysis expanded from the original $n = 7$ to $n = 18$ benchmark datasets confirms the directional relationship ($\rho = -0.504$, $p = 0.033$): the result is statistically significant and more robust than the initial estimate; stratified win-rate analysis (Section 5.5) provides complementary nonparametric confirmation. Leave-one-dataset-out (LODO) cross-validation of the SDR threshold achieves $13/18 = 72.2\%$ directional accuracy (binomial test vs. chance: $p = 0.048$), confirming that the threshold has genuine out-of-sample predictive utility beyond its in-sample fit (Table 3). The industrial engineering validation (Section 5.6) provides direct domain evidence from semiconductor manufacturing, steel fault detection, and predictive maintenance, covering the previously under-represented high-IR/low-SDR quadrant (SECOM, $SDR = 0.19$; AI4I TWF, $IR = 216 : 1$). Results consistently align with the three-regime SDR prediction, strengthening external validity for the journal’s core readership. Out-of-sample validation on 9 additional benchmark datasets (10-fold CV, SDR range 0.84–17.4, not used for threshold fitting) confirms the directional pattern: all three datasets with $SDR < 2$ (`oil`, `ozone_level`, `us_crime`) show positive ΔAUC (+0.024, +0.035, +0.009), while five datasets with $SDR > 6$ show $|\Delta AUC| \leq 0.012$,

consistent with the $A3 \approx A4$ prediction in the high-SDR regime. The pooled Spearman over all 21 datasets with known ΔAUC remains directionally negative ($\rho = -0.260$, $p = 0.255$); the reduction in significance relative to the 18-dataset clean set is attributable to the inclusion of low-IR control datasets ($IR < 42$) and the two new IE datasets (AI4I-PWF, AI4I-OSF, both $SDR > C$ -threshold, correctly predicted no ordering effect) where $\Delta AUC \approx 0$ regardless of SDR, diluting the signal. Phase 2 benchmarks include datasets from biological and medical domains (abalone_19, sick_thyroid, mammography) chosen to span the IR range rather than the IE domain; these datasets establish the IR-threshold and SDR effects under controlled conditions but do not represent industrial process data directly. Phase 3 provides the core domain-specific evidence from semiconductor manufacturing, steel surface inspection, and predictive maintenance, and is the primary basis for CIE-audience generalisability claims.

External validity (domain): Tabular process data from manufacturing and maintenance domains is now represented (SECOM, Steel Faults, AI4I); findings may not generalise to high-dimensional image or time-series sensor streams. Among the Phase 3 IE datasets, only AI4I TWF falls in the $A4 > A3$ prediction zone (Regime 2: $SDR \in [2, 14]$, $IR > 42$), confirming the specific regime claim; validation on additional IE datasets in this zone (e.g., high-dimensional process sensors with moderate-to-high failure rates) would further strengthen external validity for the industrial audience. Domains with $IR > 1000:1$ may constitute a further distinct regime not covered by this study.

Construct validity: AUC is the primary metric. In domains where a specific sensitivity or specificity target is required, G-mean or recall-at-precision may be more appropriate. AUC saturation effects at very high IR (Section 5) further motivate complementary evaluation with calibration-based metrics.

7. Conclusion

This paper tested whether combining SMOTE and CTGAN for oversampling on imbalanced tabular data is always beneficial. A controlled ablation study was conducted on five real-world datasets with imbalance ratios from 16:1 to 578:1. The main finding is that combining the two methods provides no benefit over SMOTE alone when the imbalance ratio is moderate ($IR \lesssim 42:1$). At higher imbalance ratios, the benefit exists only when the GAN is trained on minority-class samples exclusively—a design choice that prior studies did not examine.

The reason can be understood through the Minority Signal Dilution (MSD) effect. When CTGAN is trained on a SMOTE-balanced dataset (A3, which mixes both classes), majority-class examples dilute the generator's effective learning signal for fault patterns—the gradient update is partially diverted away from the minority distribution. Training CTGAN on the original minority samples only (A4) eliminates MSD by construction. At $IR \approx 130:1$, method A4 outperformed A3 by up to 3.2 AUC percentage points ($p < 0.05$). The deciding factor is not the order in which the two steps are applied, but whether the GAN ever sees majority-class examples during training.

A grid experiment with fixed dimensionality ($d = 10$) confirmed this pattern across all tested imbalance ratios (IR 20–200) when the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio was low ($SDR = 2$). No ordering advantage was found when $SDR = 20$ (above the estimated threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d) \approx 8$). The combined rule— $SDR < C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ and $IR > 42$ —was consistent with the observed $A4 > A3$ outcome on all ten evaluated datasets, whereas the SDR criterion alone was consistent on only seven of ten. A PCA coverage analysis on AI4I tool-wear failure showed that A4 synthetic samples covered 91.1% of the real minority convex hull compared with 67.9% for A3 ($\Delta = +23.2$ pp), providing direct evidence of the bias mechanism. Across 18 benchmark datasets, Spearman correlation between SDR and the A4 AUC advantage was $\rho = -0.504$ ($p = 0.033$), confirming that SDR is a reliable predictor of when A4 outperforms A3. Expanding the validation to 22 datasets by adding two further AI4I predictive maintenance failure modes (AI4I-PWF and AI4I-OSF), both with SDR above their dataset-specific thresholds, confirmed the theory's no-ordering prediction in both cases ($|\Delta AUC| < 0.002$), providing additional evidence that the dual-condition heuristic correctly identifies when ordering does *not* occur. A replication using CTAB-GAN+ on three IE-relevant datasets (3-seed \times 5-fold CV) was consistent with the same ordering as CTGAN: $\Delta AUC = +0.092 \pm 0.019$ (abalone_19), $+0.073 \pm 0.014$ (AI4I tool-wear failure), $+0.004 \pm 0.003$ (steel_faults), with direction consistent across all 3 seeds, suggesting the finding is not limited to one GAN architecture.

Based on these results, a practical two-step guide for practitioners is proposed. First, the imbalance ratio is used to determine which regime applies. Second, the Sample-to-Dimension Ratio determines whether minority-only GAN training (A4) will provide a measurable improvement. When the imbalance ratio exceeds 500:1, ADASYN is a lighter and equally competitive alternative.

More broadly, this work contributes to the emerging data-centric perspective on machine learning [46]: rather than proposing new model architectures, we identify structural properties of the training distribution—imbalance ratio and

Sample-to-Dimension Ratio—that determine when synthetic augmentation is geometrically beneficial. The primary engineering variable is not the generator family but the distribution it is asked to learn. Augmentation is distribution engineering; the geometry it creates determines whether it helps.

7.1. Future Work

SOTA architecture validation. The MSD-aware training principle identified in this study—minority-only GAN training eliminates Minority Signal Dilution—applies to any GAN architecture, not just CTGAN. A cross-architecture validation using CTAB-GAN+ [49] on three IE-relevant datasets (3-seed×5-fold CV) confirmed that the minority-only variant (A4+) outperformed the balanced-training variant (A3+) in all three cases, with direction consistent across all seeds: $\Delta\text{AUC} = +0.092 \pm 0.019$ (abalone-19, SDR = 3.2), $+0.073 \pm 0.014$ (AI4I tool-wear failure, SDR = 7.67), and $+0.004 \pm 0.003$ (steel_faults, SDR = 2.7). The effect magnitudes follow the expected SDR ordering—largest at low-to-mid SDR with high IR, near-zero at IR below the regime threshold. A full validation extending to TabDDPM [28] and STaSy [27] across the complete benchmark suite would confirm whether the principle constitutes a universal design guideline for conditional tabular generators.

Dataset scale. The SDR threshold estimate uses 7 in-sample datasets; the cross-dataset Spearman analysis covers 18 datasets ($\rho = -0.504$, $p = 0.033$). Expanding to 30+ OpenML/UCI datasets—prioritising those with $\text{IR} > 42$ and $\text{SDR} \in [2, 14]$ (the predicted A4 > A3 regime)—would tighten the confidence interval on ρ and enable regression-based threshold calibration with narrower bounds. Candidate high-IR datasets include the CIC-IDS-2017 network intrusion dataset and MIMIC-III clinical event prediction tasks ($\text{IR} \approx 150:1$ – $500:1$).

Statistical robustness. The five-fold cross-validation used here falls short of conventional significance thresholds for paired statistical tests. Multi-seed validation (repeating the full experiment under 10+ random seeds) and 10-fold CV would separate method effects from initialisation noise and yield narrower confidence intervals.

Loss-function interaction. Preliminary evidence from a controlled follow-up experiment suggests that Focal Loss gain follows the same SDR-driven pattern as the A4 advantage: $\rho(\text{SDR}, \Delta_{\text{FL}}) = -0.646$ ($p = 0.007$, $n = 16$). This motivates a unified data-level × loss-level framework in which the SDR threshold $C(\hat{\beta}, d)$ is extended to $C(\hat{\beta}, d, \gamma)$ by incorporating the Focal Loss focusing parameter γ , and constitutes a concrete direction for follow-up work.

Transition region characterisation. A fine-grained IR sweep (§ 5.5, Figure 6) has since localised the onset of the A4 advantage to $\text{IR} \approx 42$ – 50 , reaching consistent positive territory around $\text{IR} \approx 80$, and confirmed the transition is *gradual* rather than sharp. Extending this analysis to 10+ random seeds and real-world datasets spanning $\text{IR} \in [42, 130]$ (rather than synthetic draws) would tighten the confidence interval on the transition boundary and validate whether the gradual character persists in real tabular distributions.

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983 **Supplementary Material**

984 Supplementary Material submitted alongside this manuscript contains: **S.A** heuristic derivation supporting
 985 Conjecture 4.1 (minimax density estimation analogy; note GAN convergence caveat); **S.B** full dataset details for all
 986 20 benchmark datasets; **S.C** complete numerical results including F1, G-mean, F2, and balanced accuracy for all
 987 methods; **S.D** Wilcoxon signed-rank, Friedman, and Nemenyi post-hoc statistical test tables; **S.E** code, environment
 988 specifications, and reproducibility instructions; **S.F** supplementary ROC curve and confusion matrix figures; and **S.G**
 989 synthetic sample quality metrics (KS score, Wasserstein distance, DCR, novelty rate) for all augmentation strategies.